

TRENDS IN CHINESE FDI IN SOUTH AMERICA: Findings from the Regional Repository of Chinese Investments in Latin America

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The Regional Repository of Chinese Investments in Latin America is a first of its kind effort to document and visually represent Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) in the region since 2003. The project, which documents operational Chinese FDI projects in certain Latin American countries, is also a regional endeavor, having been developed by Chile's Núcleo Milenio on the Impacts of China in Latin America and the Caribbean, the Inter-American Dialogue, and a team of interdisciplinary researchers and partner institutions spanning the Americas. At present, it contains 363 projects worth \$162 billion in eight Latin American countries—Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Paraguay, Peru, and Uruguay—comprising 296 FDI projects valued at \$135 billion and 67 construction projects worth \$25.7 billion, with plans to grow the Repository to visualize Chinese investments in additional Latin American nations in the coming months.

The Repository aims to supplement existing efforts to document Chinese FDI, including by georeferencing FDI instances. Using points and vectors, the Repository's interactive map visualizes the extent of Chinese investment (greenfield, mergers and acquisitions, and joint ventures) across the region. Points represent investments in assets such as mines or real estate, while vectors represent projects that span longer distances, such as roads, railways, and participation in oil fields.

Link to the online tool:

<https://iclac.cl/eng/mapa-repositorio-regional-de-inversiones-chinas/>

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In addition to exploring the map feature, Repository users can search the site's FDI data by project type, sector, and country. The Repository's search feature also allows for comparative analysis across different investment modalities. It currently includes 156 acquisitions by Chinese companies, 106 greenfield projects, 34 joint ventures, and 67 construction projects, wherein Chinese companies retain no ownership of local assets and which are labeled distinctly from FDI projects.

Unlike most existing datasets on Chinese FDI in the region, the Repository focuses exclusively on operational projects, excluding deals that were announced, but have since been cancelled or else never materialized. In pursuit of the most up to date and accurate depiction of Chinese FDI stock in the region, our network of on-the-ground partners and researchers continuously updates the Repository's country-level data by triangulating multiple data sources and bringing local knowledge of project progress to bear.

In addition to the Repository's multiple functionalities and downloadable data, it also includes high-quality, peer-reviewed case study analysis of FDI projects, when available. This includes analysis from peer-reviewed journal articles, doctoral dissertations, think tank reports, or government documents that thoroughly examine one or more investments in the Repository.

The Repository is intended as tool for use by researchers, practitioners, and others aiming to understand key geographical, sectors, and temporal trends in Chinese investment in parts of the Latin American region. Among these trends are the following four developments in Chinese FDI, which our team of researchers has identified in the process of collecting and confirming Repository data.

1. Chinese investment has evolved over the years in several notable ways

Whether in terms of value or number of projects, Chinese FDI in South America has fluctuated over time. Chinese FDI in the countries represented in the Repository peaked in 2017 and 2018—a period when China was actively promoting the Belt and Road Initiative and related projects. Declining investment over the next few years coincided with the Covid-19 pandemic and practical constraints on international business activity. Investment volumes have recovered somewhat in recent years, but not to the levels seen in 2017 and 2018.

Figure 1.
Chinese FDI Projects in Repository Countries

Repository data also suggest a structural shift in transaction sizes over time. In 2010, the average Chinese investment in South America amounted to approximately \$1.2 billion. Since then, the annual average project size has fluctuated between \$200 and \$800 million. This trend toward smaller average transaction sizes is reflective of an apparent shift in focus from high-profile, mega-projects toward smaller, more focused investments, as described by the Inter-American Dialogue in its 2024 report, “New Infrastructure”: Emerging Trends in Chinese Foreign Direct Investment in Latin America and the Caribbean.

Repository data also reveal some trends in Chinese investment across economic sectors. Latin American energy assets have been of relatively continuous interest to Chinese investors. A total of 123 Chinese energy projects are represented in our data, accounting for 34 percent of the total number of deals struck in the eight countries analyzed since 2003 (Figure 3).

Energy-related investments are evident across nearly all countries represented in the Repository. Driven by China’s domestic energy security strategy, which has at times prioritized equity investment in overseas

assets; individual company interests; and increasingly, the Chinese government’s commercial and industrial policies, Chinese energy investors have shown enduring interest in both acquiring existing energy assets (including transmission and distribution) and developing new ones.

Although energy has been of consistent interest to Chinese investors for many years, sectors of focus for Chinese companies have also evolved somewhat since 2003. Early investments in Repository countries

tended to focus on securing natural resources, whether through acquisitions, such as Sinopec’s 2010 purchase of a minority stake in Repsol Brazil (2010, \$7100 million), or greenfield investments, such as Hebei Wenfeng’s 2012 investment in the Oso Negro Mine in Chile (\$80 million). These deals were often the product of soaring demand for resources amid China’s rapid industrialization and urbanization in the early 2000s. However, as China’s economy upgrades and diversifies, Chinese investments in South America are increasingly apparent in a wider range of economic sectors.

Figure 2.
Number of Chinese FDI Projects by Repository Country, 2004-2024

Figure 3.
Chinese FDI in Repository Countries by Sector, 2004-2024

Natural resources still factor, but Chinese capital has increasingly flowed into electricity generation and distribution, renewable energy, agricultural production, and technology infrastructure. These industries represent 6, 23, 10, and 6 percent, respectively, of total Repository deals since 2004.

Chinese companies' preferred mode of entry into the South American market has also changed somewhat over time. Until 2016, greenfield investments and acquisitions occurred in roughly equal proportions, as Chinese companies sought to both develop new assets

and acquire existing ones (see Figure 4). However, since 2016, among the eight countries represented in the Repository, acquisitions have become the dominant mode of entry. Much of this is focused on large projects in the energy and mining sectors, where Chinese companies have seemingly prioritized the purchase of established assets with proven operational capacity over the development of new projects that carry higher execution risks. As a result of the size of these projects, the value of FDI through acquisitions has exceeded the value of greenfield and joint venture projects.

Figure 4.
Chinese FDI in Repository Countries by Mode of Entry

2. Several geographical patterns are evident in Chinese FDI in South America

Chinese investors have established a significant presence across all of South America, but the distribution of FDI across the region reveals some geographic patterns and priorities. Among the eight South American countries represented in the Repository thus far, the landscape of Chinese

investment is far from uniform, with certain countries emerging as primary destinations for Chinese capital.

When viewing the Repository’s map, users will find that Brazil stands out as the primary destination for Chinese investors and construction companies in Latin America over time, with 163 projects worth \$66.3 billion—significantly more than any other South American nation (see Figure 2). Brazil alone represents nearly 45 percent of all Chinese investment and construction projects in the countries analyzed and approximately 41 percent of the total since 2003. As the region’s largest

Figure 5.
Chinese FDI in Repository Countries by Sector and Mode of Entry

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economy, Brazilian markets have been of interest to Chinese investors for decades. The country's abundant natural resources, including its critical minerals, align with China's strategic interests.

Argentina and Chile constitute the second tier of investment destinations by project count. However, when measured by overall project value, Peru emerges as the second-largest recipient of Chinese capital in the region. While fewer FDI deals have been struck in Peru than Argentina and Chile, Chinese deals in Peru tend to be of higher average value. They are focused in capital-intensive sectors such as mining and energy.

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The Repository also includes several projects that transcend national borders. Although some of China's higher-profile trans-regional projects (e.g., the Peru-Brazil Railway) have failed to materialize to date, there are many other examples of operational cross-border projects, especially in the "lithium triangle," a region encompassing parts of Argentina, Chile, and Bolivia that accounts for approximately 60 percent of the world's known lithium reserves. Chinese companies such as Ganfeng and Tianqi Lithium have engaged across the resource basin. Tianqi's acquisition of a 23.8% stake in Chile's SQM, the world's second-largest lithium producer, complemented Ganfeng's participation in the very same salt flats across the border in Argentina.

The Repository's map also reveals some clustering tendencies among Chinese investors. As in the case of lithium, clusters are most often related to the positioning of natural resource endowments. Energy investments by companies such as China Three Gorges and State Grid are concentrated in northeast Brazil, which has favorable conditions for wind power and other renewable energy projects. In this region and elsewhere, Chinese companies have invested across the energy ecosystem—in power generation, but also in the transmission infrastructure needed to deliver electricity to Brazil's population centers.

Chinese agro-industrial investments are generally clustered in northeastern Argentina, southern Brazil, and Uruguay. These include investments in soybean and meat processing, agricultural logistics, and other agro-industrial ventures. COFCO, China's largest grains trader, has been active across this region and beyond, especially in developing logistical infrastructure to better connect South American agricultural production to Chinese consumers. There are also instances where different companies work to develop raw materials and related infrastructure sometimes in coordination.

China's investments, especially those covering long distances, which are represented as vectors in the Repository map, can play a significant role in reshaping economic geography. This includes the emergence of new development corridors that change the relative accessibility of certain geographies.

3. Chinese state-owned enterprises continue to play a dominant role in Chinese FDI in South America

Just over a dozen, mostly state-owned Chinese companies are responsible for a considerable portion of total Chinese FDI in the eight countries currently represented in the Repository. Three Chinese state-owned enterprises stand out as major investors in South America, whether in terms of the number of projects in which they are involved or total capital invested. These "big three" include State Grid, China Three Gorges, and Sinopec. Since 2004, each has invested more than \$12 billion in Repository countries (see Figure 6).

Figure 6.
Chinese Companies Operating in Repository Countries

State Grid, one of world's largest utility companies, has focused on electricity transmission and distribution, with a focus on Brazil. Its investments include the 2018 acquisition of a controlling stake in CPFL Energia, Brazil's largest private electricity company, and major investments in long-distance, ultra-high-voltage transmission lines that connect the remote Belo Monte hydroelectric plant to Brazilian population centers.

China Three Gorges, which operates the dam by the same name in China's Hubei province has acquired and developed hydroelectric assets throughout the region since 2013. Its portfolio includes major Brazilian hydroelectric facilities acquired from Duke Energy, including the Jupía and Ilha Solteira dams, as well as investments in Peru, Chile, and Argentina.

Sinopec, one of China's national oil companies (NOCs), has focused to a considerable degree on Brazil, where its strategy has evolved over time from an early focus on upstream assets (oil fields and production facilities) to investments across the petroleum value chain, including refining and distribution networks. As noted in Figure 6, Sinopec has invested approximately the same dollar value in South America as State Grid and China Three Gorges, but maintains fewer overall projects.

Beyond these three major investors are over a dozen other companies that have developed and maintained a substantial presence in South America in just a matter of years, in some cases. Fourteen companies have at least five separate investment projects in the region and/or total investments exceeding \$4 billion. In raw materials extraction, Gezhouba, China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC), Aluminium Corporation of China, China National Offshore Oil Corporation (CNOOC), Ganfeng Lithium, Sinohydro, and China General Nuclear Power Corporation feature in this group. Grains trader COFCO is also among these large investors. And in manufacturing and technology, BYD, Power China, CSR Sifang (railway equipment),

Tencent, Fosun and Huawei all feature. Together, the "big three" and these other large investors account for 32 percent of all Chinese investment projects documented in the Repository. What is more, they account for approximately 60 percent (\$161 billion, by our estimates) of the total value of Chinese investment in the countries represented in the Repository.

Policy mandates would appear to have directed Chinese investment into certain strategic sectors in the countries represented, including resource acquisition and now, market-seeking investment for a wide range of increasingly high-value-added goods. Additionally, the dominance of large state-owned enterprises means that a significant portion of Chinese investment in the region is operating with time horizons, risk tolerance, and strategic objectives that presumably differ from those of commercial investors, whether Chinese or otherwise. Regardless of their ownership structures, the outsize presence of these top investors in certain industries is thought to affect sectoral and other decision-making across the region.

4. Academic analysis of Chinese FDI in South America remains limited

Despite the extent of Chinese investment in South America, few of these investments have been subject to rigorous academic or policy analysis. The Repository includes case studies (peer-reviewed academic articles, doctoral dissertations, substantive think tank reports, and government analyses) in Spanish, Portuguese, English, and Chinese of Chinese investments in the eight countries surveyed. Of the 363 investment and construction projects represented in our database, only 113 (31 percent) have been studied in much detail. Moreover, many of the projects that lack corresponding

studies involve substantial capital commitments or are in sectors of strategic importance.

Among existing studies of Chinese projects, there are some notable asymmetries along both linguistic and geographical lines. In Chinese-language academic and policy literature, research tends to focus predominantly on investments by large Chinese state-owned enterprises, particularly electric utilities such as State Grid, China Southern Power Grid, and China Three

Gorges. This focus likely reflects both the strategic importance of these sectors in China's economic planning and the greater availability of information on these high-profile state champions.

By contrast, English-language and Spanish-language research gravitate toward projects that have encountered significant technical difficulties, generated environmental controversies, or generated other problems.

Table 1.
Highly-Researched Chinese Investment Projects in South America, 2004-2024

Project Name	Year	Number of Case Studies
The Cónдор Cliff (Nestor Kirchner) and Barrancosa (Jorge Cepernic) dams in Argentina, developed as a joint venture between Chinese companies and local firm Electroingeniería	2015	16
Argentina's Belgrano Cargas railway system	2013	8
Bolivia's Misicuni Multiple Dam construction project	2015	5
Tianqi Lithium's acquisition of a minority stake in Chile's SQM lithium producer	2016- 2018	7
Hydroelectric projects in Ecuador, including the Coca Codo Sinclair, Delsitanisagua, and Minas de San Francisco power plants	2010- 2012	24
Ecuador's ECU 911 citizen security system	2012	8
Construction and repair of multiple highways in Ecuador	2014	8
The Mirador mining project in Ecuador	2014	16
The acquisition of Glencore's Las Bambas mining assets in Peru	2014	13
Petroleum sector acquisitions in Peru, including Petrobras Energía Perú	2013, 2014	8
The expansion of Peru's Chancay Port Terminal	2020	9
The Toromocho mine expansion in Peru	2018	13
The expansion of the Marcona mine in Peru	2022	14

Additionally, investments in certain countries—Brazil and Argentina, for instance—have received far more research attention than those in other countries in the Repository. Important Chinese investments in other countries have occasionally proceeded with minimal scrutiny.

Finally, we found that much of the existing case study analysis is focused on just a small subset of high-profile projects. Our data show that nearly half of all Repository case studies are focused on just seventeen projects—fewer than 5 percent of total investments represented in the Repository (see Table 1).

The prevalence or lack of project-level analysis has implications for regional stakeholders, especially to the extent that analysis of project progress and outcomes informs policymaking around foreign investment regulations, sectoral development strategies, and negotiation with Chinese investors. Robust studies of projects across the region can provide local decision-makers with benchmarks for evaluating proposals or structuring agreements that maximize local benefits. For civil society organizations, these sorts of studies are critical to understanding and tracking developments in Chinese corporate behavior. For the academic community, the concentration of research on a small subset of projects limits theoretical development and empirical testing related to Chinese outbound investment. Finally, for Chinese investors, research gaps represent a missed opportunity to learn from past experiences and improve practices.

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What factors will shape future Chinese investment?

Several factors are likely to influence the evolution of Chinese investment in new and impactful ways in the coming years. These include China's own domestic economic transformation. Traditional resource-seeking investments in extractive industries will continue to be important to China but will increasingly be accompanied by market-seeking investments that support China's efforts to upgrade its economy.

Those South American countries with considerable potential for renewable energy development and digital transformation may see accelerated Chinese

investment interest, as China looks to export high-tech equipment and services. At the same time, the critical minerals and metals that supply China's high-tech revolution will also be of continued interest to Chinese investors, if recent Repository data is any indication.

Host country policy will also continue to shape outcomes across the region. As South American governments develop more sophisticated approaches to managing Chinese investment—including possible screening mechanisms, sector-specific regulations, and frameworks for strategic partnerships—we should expect to see greater divergence in investment patterns across countries. Increasingly, those nations offering stable policy environments, clear regulatory frameworks, and strategic alignment with Chinese priorities have attracted a larger share of investment flows.

The broader geopolitical context will also influence Chinese investment decisions and outcomes in South America. A period of heightened US-China tension may lead Chinese investors or host governments to approach sensitive sectors with greater caution. At the same time, strategic competition and an evolving trade landscape could accelerate Chinese and host government efforts to secure and diversify economic partnerships throughout the region.

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